

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING PSYCHOLOGY IN THE TRAINING OF PEDAGOGUES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of the psychology in pedagogy. The effectiveness of the methods applied by a number of specialists is researched and discussions about new methods are described.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, the concept of psychology, the human factor, systematic influence, psyche, methods.*

INTRODUCTION. Before connecting pedagogy with the concept of psychology, it is necessary to have information about this concept. According to information in books written by scientists, psychology studies the human mind and how the human brain behaves in different situations. We know that activity in the field of pedagogy also relies on the human factor. More precisely, it is important for pedagogues to study the psychology of students before teaching them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. According to scientific researches and information of scientists, the teacher has a systematic influence on the students in order to give them knowledge, make them informative, and educate them. Psyche in this based on logic and social factors. That is, in order to know the effect of the influence, it determines the influence plan based on knowing how student's intuition, perception, imagination, attention and thinking process are going. In particular, it is necessary for the teacher to have deep psychology of young people. A teacher who knows this well approaches the child taking into account the age and individual characteristics of each child and can effectively influence him. As the study of children's psyche plays an important role in the effective education of children, therefore, it is necessary to use the most suitable and effective methods for teaching psychology to pedagogues in depth.

SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL APPROACH. As we mentioned above, several effective methods of teaching psychology have been identified and put into practice by a number of scientists and specialists. There are the following:

1. „Ajour saw” method. This word means „ajour” (in French) „passing from one side to another, open on both sides”. In this methods, students are divided in to small groups and text tasks are distributed to them by the teacher. Students discuss the given tasks and share information with each other.

2. „Synectics” method. This method is practical, suitable for seminars and laboratory exercises, and is close to the „brainstorming” method. In this case, the student puts forward his thoughts and views based on analogy regarding the solution of the problem set in the lesson. In this case, the analogy can be direct, personal, symbolic and imaginary.

3. „Beehive” method. The problem is discussed in one group or in two small groups. In this case, the tasks can be different or one for the whole group. Groups discuss the given problem for a certain period of time and report the result to others. The best solution to the problem is selected.

These methods are only part of it. I summarize below the effective methods of teaching psychology in the training of teachers that I would recommend

1. „Scene view” method. To use this method the teacher assigns each student a specific situations related to the teacher and the student, and the student performs the solution of the given problem in the form of the scene. By applying this method in practice, an effective environment is created for future pedagogues to solve their profession and problems and to work well with students.

2. „Didactic games” method. In this method, the teacher organizes games for students on topics related to children’s psychology. These games should mainly be games for children of small age and school age. Games like these help students understand children and their psychology.

3. „Chain” method. In the chain method, students learn all subjects in connection with psychology. It is natural that more and higher skills and psychological qualifications are required from teachers in higher education. This method is useful for students to learn psychology of all subjects.

RESULTS. In general, the use of practice in teaching in every field gives effective results. Therefore, in teaching psychology in pedagogy, it is more effective to use practical methods than simple lessons based on theoretical terms and rules of psychology. Having listed several such methods above it is necessary to research how effective they are and what positive results they can show.

Firstly. Through practical methods, students will be able to improve their teamwork and leadership skills. Examples of this are „Ajour saw” and „Beehive” methods. These methods are based on working with a group.

Secondly. Students develop their teaching skills in an environment that is convenient for them. The „Scene view” method helps them in this.

Thirdly. Students study psychology in connection with other subjects, and this helps to develop skills in other areas. For this, the „Chain” method should be used.

CONCLUSION. According to all scientific researches, studies and scientific-practical approaches, we can come to the following conclusions: Psychology plays an important role in the training of pedagogues in higher education, because education and training always be side by side, and training is closely related to the human psyche. Therefore, pedagogues need to be not only teachers, but also psychologists. If future pedagogues are not given information about psychology, they may face various problems later in their careers. So that, psychology should be a side subject in improving the professional skills of pedagogues.

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